

JEFF-4.0 for nuclide inventory and waste management: a first use of JEFF-4.0 data for Fission Pulse with MENDEL

Sébastien Lahaye^{1,*}, Tan-Dat Huynh¹

¹Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, Service d'Études des Réacteurs et de Mathématiques Appliquées, 91191, Gif-sur-Yvette, France

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803526

ABSTRACT

MENDEL is the new generation nuclide inventory and source term generation code system in CEA, France, successor to DARWIN/PEPIN2. Since MENDEL v3.2, released in 2024, its capabilities are equivalent to DARWIN/PEPIN2.4.8, enabling all the industrial and research users of DARWIN/PEPIN2 to change for MENDEL.

2025 has seen the official release of JEFF-4 (Joint Evaluated Fission and Fusion) Nuclear Data library. Cross-sections, but also nuclear constant data have been renewed in this new Joint European evaluation. The use of JEFF-4 and its comparison to other nuclear data evaluations is part of the Verification and Validation process around reactor physics code in order to justify the choice of JEFF-4 as the new recommended library.

Until MENDEL v3.2, JEFF-3.1.1 was considered as the recommended nuclear data evaluation for CEA's fuel cycle and waste management studies concerning nuclear data constants, as JEFF-3.2 and JEFF-3.3 improvements were done mostly on cross-sections and neutronics oriented nuclear data.

With the official JEFF-4.0 evaluation, and after preliminary tests done during the JEFF-4.0 production with test-versions, we present in this paper a comparison on decay heat data with some of the most internationally used evaluations: ENDF/B-VII.1, ENDF/B-VIII.0, JEFF-3.1.1, JENDL-4.0 and JEFF-4.

In order to focus on nuclear constant data, we decided to focus on Fission Pulse Experiments. By doing so, we can observe the impact of Independent Fission Yields, Half-Lives, Decay Branching Ratios and Decay Energies on some old but solid benchmarks with experimental data.

Keywords: Nuclear data, Fission yields, Fission pulse

1. INTRODUCTION

In 2025 was officially released the new European nuclear data evaluation JEFF-4.0 [1]. In the verification and validation process of the inventory and source term generation code MENDEL [2], it was decided to use this new evaluation in a first application which will not depend on neutronics calculation options, in order to verify in a first step the nuclear constant data (half-lives, decay energies, decay branching ratio and independent fission yields), without looking at the cross-section data. For such cases, fission pulse experiments appear as a natural test case.

Fission pulse experiments were conducted in the 80's, and consist of a simple yet important series of benchmarks with experimental data for fuel cycle studies, giving decay heat experimental data for short cooling times. We define as fissile system a fission of a particular fissile isotope with a particular incident neutron energy (typically thermal, fast or high energy incident neutrons). Incident neutron is characterized as thermal, fast or high energy in the nuclear data evaluation files, and one fissile system corresponds to one set of independent fission yields. For fast fission pulses, experimental data were obtained in particular in the fast neutron facility YAYOI in Japan [3] and conglomerated by Akiyama [4,

*sebastien.lahaye@cea.fr

5, 6]. For thermal fission pulse, different experimental data have been published, one of the most cited being Dickens [7, 8], several experiments have been conglomerated by Tobias [9]. For Akiyama data, energy release (decay heat data) is separated between decay heat due to beta and gamma decays.

Decay Heat values for fission pulses are given for cooling times going from roughly 1 s to 10 000 s through different sources, among them the IAEA/CoNDERC project [10].

For fission pulse computation, we model the fission pulse by cooling an inventory of radioactive isotopes which concentrations, at time zero, correspond to the independent fission yield of the observed fissile system (for example, fission products from ^{239}Pu fast fission).

During the cooling phase, isotopic concentration $N_i(t)$ of isotope i is computed in MENDEL (as in DARWIN/PEPIN2) with an analytic solutions of Bateman equations. Decay constants λ_i and decay branching ratio $br_{j \rightarrow i}$ from isotope j to i are taken into account:

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt}(t) = -\lambda_i N_i(t) + \sum_{j \neq i} b_{j \rightarrow i} \lambda_j N_j(t) \quad (1)$$

In DARWIN/PEPIN2, this analytical solution is available only for cooling. In MENDEL, it is available as long as the depletion matrix is triangular, which is always the case for cooling.

The calculation of decay heat use isotopic concentrations at a given time $N_i(t)$, half-lives and total decay energies E_i as Decay Heat reads:

$$DH(t) = \sum_i N_i(t) \lambda_i E_i \quad (2)$$

In order to observe the impact of the nuclear data evaluation's choice on Decay Heat value, we took into consideration:

- American evaluation ENDF-B/VII.1 [11] and ENDF-B/VIII.0 [12],
- Japanese evaluation JENDL-4.0 [13],
- CEA evaluation CEA5.1.2, based on JEFF-3.1.1 [14], and noted JEFF-3.1.1 on the rest of the paper,
- The new Joint Evaluated Fusion and Fission Nuclear Data JEFF-4.0 [1].

With those evaluated data, we simulated for this paper decays for fission pulses corresponding to seven fission systems: fast and thermal ^{235}U fission pulses, fast and thermal ^{239}Pu fission pulses, as well as fast ^{238}U , ^{237}Np and ^{238}Np fission pulses. As we had only graphs and no numerical data available for ^{237}Np and ^{238}Np fission pulses, those results are not shown in this paper.

2. COMPARING EXPERIMENTS WITH COMPUTATIONS

In this section, we compare, for each fissile system considered in this study, the impact of JEFF-4 compared to the other international nuclear data evaluations, and compared to the experimental data.

Decay Heat after fission pulses have been computed with both DARWIN/PEPIN2 and MENDEL. The results are so close it was decided to show only MENDEL's results. A development version has been used for this version due to some improvements created specifically for this work.

When both fundamental level and first metastable level isotopes are described in a nuclear data evaluation, it can appear that only independent fission yield on the fundamental state is given in the evaluation data file. Modeling may vary according to the code used. In DARWIN/PEPIN2, by default, the independent fission yields are split in 50% to the fundamental state and 50% to the metastable state isotope when one of the fission yield is unknown. In MENDEL, by default, 100% is left to the described fundamental state, and the first metastable isotope is not produced directly by fission.

With JEFF-3.1.1, those differences in modeling have some visible impacts [15].

With JEFF-4.0, those differences showed no impact on the analysed configurations. It is due to a better knowledge of independent fission yields concerning the metastable state fission products.

As DARWIN/PEPIN2 and MENDEL give the same results, we show only MENDEL's results on this paper.

2.1. ^{235}U fast and thermal fission pulses

When looking at ^{235}U fast and thermal fissions, we have data both for thermal [8, 9] and fast [6] fission pulses. We represent in Figures 1 the Decay Heat integrated over time for all evaluated nuclear data used in this paper and the experimental data.

Figure 1. Decay Heat after a ^{235}U thermal (left) and fast (right) fission pulse.

We observe on thermal fission a smaller discrepancy between JEFF-3.1.1 and ENDF/B results on the [10-100] s cooling time than between JEFF-4.0 and ENDF/B results. The discrepancy before 10 s is left similar. When comparing to experimental data values, JEFF-4.0 is in very good agreement with DICKENS experimental data on cooling times before 100 s, which was less the case with JEFF-3.1.1. After 100 s, all computations using the different nuclear data evaluations give similar Decay Heat values.

Concerning the fast fission pulse, we observe differences up to 100 s. On the experimental data cooling times, we observe an improvement on total Decay Heat between 100 s and 1000 s, when a discrepancy can be seen with JEFF-3.1.1.

On ^{235}U fast fission pulse, the use of JEFF-4.0 seems to reduce the discrepancies with experimental data. On ^{235}U thermal fission pulse, the effect is less visible.

2.2. ^{239}Pu fast and thermal fission pulses

As for ^{239}Pu fast and thermal fission pulses, we show in Figures 2 the Decay Heat integrated for ^{239}Pu over time for all evaluated nuclear data used in this paper and the experimental data.

For thermal fission pulse, we observe a less important discrepancy between JEFF-3.1.1 and JEFF-4.0 than observed for ^{235}U . Around 1000 s after the pulse, the only period where JEFF-3.1.1 was slightly out of the DICKENS data uncertainty bars, JEFF-4.0 barely enters the experimental error bars.

For fast fission pulse, we also observe an improvement between 300 s and 4000 s when comparing JEFF-3.1.1 and JEFF-4.0. This improvement makes the JEFF-4.0 Decay Heat similar to ENDF/B and JENDL results.

On ^{239}Pu thermal and fast fission pulses, the use of JEFF-4.0 reduce significantly the distance to experi-

Figure 2. Decay Heat after a ^{239}Pu thermal (left) and fast (right) fission pulse.

mental data. All JEFF-4.0 results are in the experimental error bars.

2.3. ^{233}U and ^{238}U fast fission pulses

Data from Akiyama [6] also gives experimental values for ^{233}U and ^{238}U fast fission pulses. We compare those data with results from international nuclear data evaluations in Figures 3.

Figure 3. Decay Heat after a ^{233}U (left) and a ^{238}U fast fission pulse.

For ^{233}U fast fission pulse, while we observe a Decay Heat with JEFF-4.0 nearer the experimental value than with JEFF-3.1.1 for cooling times over 1000 s, cooling times before 200 s show a decrease in total Decay Heat, and some cooling times are now out of the experimental error bars. It is particularly true for cooling times at 26, 45 and 70 seconds. Before 100 s, the experimental data are oscillating from one cooling time measurement to another. In order to conclude between a real underestimation of the Decay Heat due to JEFF-4.0 and a problem on the data, it would be interesting to obtain other data dealing with ^{233}U fast fission. As this fission system is not important for PWR nor SFR if we do not use Thorium fuel, this artifact is considered as secondary on this paper. Nevertheless, if a Thorium based fuel is used with JEFF-4.0 and short time Decay Heat is computed, it will be necessary to reassess this question.

Concerning ^{238}U fast fission pulse, the differences between nuclear data evaluation data on measurement cooling time is very limited. On Short cooling times (less than 20 s) JEFF-4.0 curves is similar to JENDL-4.0.

3. ZOOM ON ^{239}Pu FAST FISSION PULSE

We focus on this section on ^{239}Pu fast fission pulse, which is an important fission for fast reactors, and for which we have good consolidated data with Akiyama values. Those data include a differentiation between Decay Heat issued from β and γ decays [4, 5].

Due to the absence of any major α producer in the nuclides produced by fission pulse, the α Decay Heat is negligible, as seen as in Figure 4, where the percentage of α , β and γ Decay Heat is plotted in time. In order to obtain a smooth curve and observe for both short and long cooling time, we show the components on MENDEL's Decay Heat using JEFF4 nuclear data evaluation.

Figure 4. Percentage of Decay Heat coming due to α , β and γ decays in MENDEL's Decay Heat results from JEFF4 nuclear data evaluation on ^{239}Pu fast fission pulse.

This demonstrates that the analysis of β and γ Decay Heat is sufficient on this application. This is valid for all actinides' fission pulse, regardless the fissile system.

We represent in Figures 5 the β Decay Heat (on the left) and the γ Decay Heat (on the right) for all evaluated nuclear data libraries as well as the experimental data available.

Figure 5. Decay Heat after a ^{239}Pu fast fission pulse for Beta (left) and Gamma (right) rays.

Due to the pandemonium effect, JEFF-3.1.1 tends to under-estimate the γ Decay Heat by up to 10% for cooling times under 2000 s, leading to a 10% over estimation of the β Decay Heat (better measurement of the total Decay Heat). The pandemonium effect is reduced with JEFF-4.0 and the other recent international nuclear data evaluations.

The total Decay Heat (Fig.2 right) was more or less inside the experimental error bars for both JEFF-3.1.1

and JEFF-4.0. For JEFF-3.1.11, it was mainly due to compensation effects.

With JEFF-4.0, we observe that both β and γ Decay Heat values are much more in agreement with Akiyama data [4, 5], which is not the case using JEFF-3.1.1 nuclear data.

3.1. γ Decay Heat

We first look for the origins of the differences between JEFF-3.1.1 and JEFF-4.0 on the γ Decay Heat.

At 2000 s, the first contributor to Decay Heat is ^{104}Tc ($T_{1/2} \approx 1000$ s), for which we observe a 63% increase with JEFF-4.0. This increase in itself explains 6% of the total increase of γ Decay Heat. The independent fission yield producing ^{104}Tc from a ^{239}Pu fast fission is 30% higher with JEFF-4.0 than with JEFF-3.1.1. Furthermore, β and γ mean decay energies have also been reevaluated. If the β energy has been reduced by 40%, the γ energy is increased by 70%.

This modification on both the ^{104}Tc independent fission yield and decay energy explain most of the JEFF-4.0 value around 1000 s to 2000 s.

At 70 s, on the first pike on the γ Decay Heat curve of Figure 5 (right), more contributing isotopes evolve between JEFF-3.1.1 and JEFF-4.0:

- ^{106}Tc , representing 6.3% of the total Decay Heat in JEFF-3.1.1, increases by 32%,
- ^{140}Cs , representing 5.4% of the total Decay Heat in JEFF-3.1.1, increases by 7%,
- ^{144}La , representing 5.3% of the total Decay Heat in JEFF-3.1.1, increases by 7%,
- ^{105}Mo , representing 3.2% of the total Decay Heat in JEFF-3.1.1, increases by a factor 4.

In the same time, other nuclides emit less Decay Heat with JEFF-4.0, like ^{103}Mo , ^{91}Rb or ^{98}Nb .

In the particular case of ^{105}Mo , the γ mean decay energy has been increased by a factor 4.36 between JEFF-3.1.1 and JEFF-4.0, while the β decay energy decreases by roughly 45%. The total decay energy ($\beta + \gamma$) changes by a 40% increase.

Considering ^{106}Tc , the total decay is increased by 11% with JEFF-4.0, with a 43% increase of the γ decay energy and a 25% decrease of the β decay energy.

Those differences, if individually less important than the ^{106}Tc at 2000 s, explain the modification of γ Decay Heat at around 70 s between JEFF-3.1.1 and JEFF-4.0.

3.2. β Decay Heat

When looking at the β Decay Heat, we do not observe pikes as clearly as for γ Decay Heat during the lapse of cooling time of the experimental data.

We focus on the 1000 s cooling time, where JEFF-3.1.1 shows a clear pike.

At this particular time, ^{104}Tc is the second main contributor to β Decay Heat with JEFF-3.1.1, while it is only fifth contributor with JEFF-4.0. We observe different trends for Tc isotopes:

- ^{102}Tc does not change significantly (0.5% increase),
- ^{104}Tc decreases by 44%,
- ^{105}Tc decreases by 43%

Globally, β Decay Heat decreases due to a significant decrease in β decay energies. For Tc isotopes, it is particularly true from isotopes ^{104}Tc to ^{108}Tc .

3.3. Mean decay energies in JEFF-4.0

In Figure 6, we represent histograms for the distribution of β and γ mean decay energy values in JEFF-3.1.1 and JEFF-4 evaluations. The x-axis describes the log of the mean decay energy, while the y-axis gives the number of data in each histogram's bin. We can confirm that there is no concrete trend in the modifications from JEFF-3.1.1 and JEFF-4.0. The energy decay values are not modified enough to observe a huge discrepancy on those histograms.

Figure 6. Distributions of β (left) and γ (right) mean decay energies in JEFF-3.1.1 and JEFF-4.0. The x value is the \log_{10} value of the actual energy. The y axis stands for the number of data in each bin.

Nevertheless, those modifications, concerning few nuclides, explain the discrepancies observed for ^{239}Pu fast fission pulse, and make the JEFF-4.0 data library better for this particular case, when validating with the literature [4, 5].

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work shows a first use, in MENDEL, of the Joint Evaluated Fusion and Fission Data Library JEFF-4.0, released in 2025.

JEFF-4.0 for MENDEL is available through the DARWIN/PEPIN2 JEFF-4.0 library and through the yet experimental MENDEL library containing JEFF-4.0 (HDF format).

This new HDF library will be released with the future MENDEL version 4.0, scheduled for 2027, but is already usable in previous versions of MENDEL. For this work, we used it exclusively, not using as in previous MENDEL's versions the ASCII files to initialize the concentration for fission pulses.

MENDEL is now able to load all nuclear constant data (isotopic half-lives, energies, branching ratios, independent fission yields...) in a single Nuclear Data Library. This choice, rather than multiple ASCII files, is of the utmost importance to ensure the coherence of the different nuclear data used in any calculations, by reducing the number of files managed by users.

Given the first results obtained by JEFF-4.0 on fission pulse computations compared to experimental data, the validation of the use of this new library will be continued in the near future. JEFF-4.0 might soon become the recommended nuclear data evaluation when using MENDEL, in replacement of JEFF-3-based libraries, currently used in CEA's neutronics and fuel cycle calculation options.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank EDF and Framatome for their invaluable support in the development of the MENDEL code.

REFERENCES

- [1] Joint Evaluated Fission and Fusion Project. "JEFF-4.0 Evaluated Data: neutron data." Technical report, OCDE (2025).
- [2] A. Tsilanizara, R. Baron, T. Huynh, and S. Lahaye. "MENDEL: Overview of the Capabilities for Fuel Cycle Analysis." In *PHYSOR 2026*. Torino, Italy (2026).
- [3] Y. Ohkawachi and A. Shono. "Decay heat measurement of actinides at YAYOI." *Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology, Supplement*, **volume 2**, pp. 493–496 (2002).
- [4] M. Akiyama, K. Furuta, T. Ida, K. Sakata, and S. An. "Measurements of Beta-Ray Decay Heat of Fission Products for Fast Neutron Fission of ^{235}U , ^{239}Pu , and ^{233}U ." *J Atomic Ener Soc Japan*, **volume 24**(10), pp. 803 – 816 (1982). In Japanese.
- [5] M. Akiyama, K. Furuta, T. Ida, K. Sakata, and S. An. "Measurements of Gamma-Ray Decay Heat of Fission Products for Fast Neutron Fission of ^{235}U , ^{239}Pu , and ^{233}U ." *J Atomic Ener Soc Japan*, **volume 24**(9), pp. 709 – 722 (1982). In Japanese.
- [6] M. Akiyama, Y. Oka, and S. An. "Measurement of decay heat of fast neutron fission products." *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, **volume 32**(1), pp. 53 – 60 (1998).
- [7] J. Dickens, J. Emery, and T. Love. "Fission product energy release for times following thermal neutron fission of $^{239,241}\text{Pu}$ between 2 and 14 000 seconds." *Nucl Sci Eng*, **volume 78**, p. 126 (1981).
- [8] J. Dickens, T. Love, J. McConnell, and R. Peelle. "Fission product energy release for times following thermal neutron fission of ^{235}U between 2 and 14 000 seconds." *Nucl Sci Eng*, **volume 74**, pp. 106–129 (1980).
- [9] A. Tobias. "Derivation of Decay Heat Benchmark for U235 and Pu239 by a Least Squares Fit to Measured Data." Technical Report CEGB report RD/B/6210/R89, United Kingdom Atomic Energy Agency (1989).
- [10] IAEA. "Compilation of Nuclear Data Experiments for Radiation Characterisation (CoNDERC)." (2026). URL <https://nds.iaea.org/conderc/>.
- [11] M. Chadwick and M. Herman. "ENDF/B-VII.1 Nuclear Data for Science and Technology: Cross Sections, Covariances, Fission Product Yields and Decay Data." *Nuclear Data Sheets*, **volume 112**, pp. 2887–2996 (2011).
- [12] D. A. Brown, M. B. Chadwick, R. Capote, A. Kahler, A. Trkov, M. Herman, A. Sonzogni, Y. Danon, A. Carlson, M. Dunn, et al. "ENDF/B-VIII. 0: the 8th major release of the nuclear reaction data library with CIELO-project cross sections, new standards and thermal scattering data." *Nuclear Data Sheets*, **volume 148**, pp. 1–142 (2018).
- [13] K. O. IWAMOTO, et al. "JENDL-4.0: A New Library for Nuclear Science and Engineering." *Journal of Nuclear Science Technology*, **volume 44**, pp. 1131–1141 (2007).
- [14] M.A. Kellett and O. Bersillon and R.W. Mills. "The JEFF-3.1/-3.1.1 Radioactive Decay Data and Fission Yields Sub-libraries." Technical Report JEFF Report 20, NEA N° 6287, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2009).
- [15] S. Lahaye, P. Bellier, H. Mao, A. Tsilanizara, and Y. Kawamoto. "First Verification and Validation Steps of MENDEL Release V1.0 Cycle Code System." In *PHYSOR 2014* (2014). Kyoto, Japan.